

INTERLINEAR TRANSLATION

ACROSS THE MUSLIM WORLD

A Comparative Perspective

Themed Section

edited by

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Surau Texts Translated: *Translation in Form, Textual Analysis in Substance*

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Abstract

This article investigates the translation tradition of *surau* communities in the Minangkabau world, with a focus on interlinear translation. With its prominent role in the Islamization of the region, the *surau* held an important historical function as a vital centre for the production, teaching, learning, and preservation of Islamic manuscripts—mostly composed in Arabic, while those written in Malay are filled with rich Arabic concepts, vocabulary, and technical expressions. As such, translation emerges as an integral aspect of engagement with the manuscripts, supporting both comprehension and instruction. Focusing on the manuscript collection of Surau Simaung in Sijunjung, West Sumatra, the study explores two central questions: first, the role and positioning of Arabic and Malay within the translation practices of *surau* manuscripts; and second, the origins of grammatical literalism, a feature often associated with interlinear translation in the *surau* tradition. This study shows that translation practices in the *surau* were diverse, encompassing holistic, running-sequential, and interlinear paradigms. Among these, occasional interlinear translation predominates, revealing a distinctive form of grammatical literalism rooted in the Arabic linguistic structure, reflective of post-classical scholarly practices. Rather than producing idiomatic Malay renderings, *surau* scholars pursued rigorous grammatical engagement with Arabic texts, transforming translation into a tool of learning and inquiry. Translation was not primarily about finding lexical equivalents in Malay but was fundamentally an exercise in textual analysis. It served as a vernacular expression of the post-classical Islamic intellectual project—*translation in form, textual analysis in substance*.

Keywords: Surau, Minangkabau, translation, literalism, textual analysis

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Introduction

This article examines the tradition of translating Arabic texts into Malay within the Minangkabau world (*Alam Minangkabau*). The Minangkabau are an ethnic group inhabiting the central region of the island of Sumatra. They refer to their homeland as *Alam Minangkabau*, which encompasses the highland heartland villages in the Bukit Barisan mountain range—known as *Darek*—as well as the expanding coastal regions to the east and west, referred to as *Rantau*.² Although the Minangkabau are today commonly associated with the province of West Sumatra, this association is “arbitrary and a shadow of colonial partitioning.”³ The language spoken in

Fig. 1 The Province of West Sumatra in Indonesia, which is currently strongly associated with the Minangkabau region.

this region is Minangkabau, a variety or dialect of Malay. It is predominantly oral in character, with a strong cultural emphasis on oral eloquence and a rich oral literary tradition.⁴ While the Minangkabau language has distinctive features of its own, the shared use of Arabic script in the writing system of both Minangkabau and Malay prior to the dominance of the Roman script further blurred the boundaries between the two.⁵

There is a record of Islamization of one of the Minangkabau kings through marriage with a sister of Sultan Mansur Syah of Melaka (1459–1477),⁶ yet it seems that

2 M Yusuf, ed., *Katalogus Manuskrip dan Skriptorium Minangkabau* (C-DATS-TUFS, 2006), 1; Jeffrey Hadler, *Muslims and Matriarchs: Cultural Resilience in Indonesia through Jihad and Colonialism* (Cornell University Press, 2008), 3, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7591/j.ctt7zc7n>.

3 Hadler, *Muslims and Matriarchs*, 4.

4 Khaidir Anwar, “Minangkabau, Background of the Main Pioneers of Modern Standard Malay in Indonesia,” *Archipel* 12, no. 1 (1976): 83, <https://doi.org/10.3406/arch.1976.1296>.

5 P Voorhoeve, *Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Sumatra*, Bibliographical Series 1 (Netherlands: 1955), 16.

6 Jane Drakard, “A Kingdom of Words: Minangkabau Sovereignty in Sumatran History” (Ph.D.

surau, a traditional Islamic learning institution in the region, is more responsible for the Islamization of the region than politics. The reason is that, on the one hand, the loyalty of the Minangkabau community was more closely aligned with the *nagari* (villages) than with the central authority of the kingdom; and on the other hand, most *surau* were rooted in the *nagari* and local market networks.⁷ This suggests that the spread of Islam in Minangkabau was shaped more by grassroots religious education and local sociocultural structures than by top-down political initiatives.

Integral to the *surau*'s role in the Islamization of the region is their historical function as vital centres for the production, teaching, learning, and preservation of Islamic manuscripts.⁸ Functioning as scriptoria, *surau* not only stored manuscripts but also fostered vibrant intellectual activity through live oral instruction.⁹ The digital collections of Minangkabau manuscripts preserved across several platforms—such as the Leiden Digital Collection, the Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library, and the DREAMSEA Project—stand as testament to the unparalleled importance of the *surau* in the Minangkabau manuscript tradition. Local accounts and catalogues also document private collections, yet these manuscripts are typically inherited from *surau* or from the leaders of a *ṭarīqa* associated with a particular *surau*.¹⁰

The majority of *surau* manuscripts bear strong pedagogical characteristics, often taking the form of personal or instructional notes.¹¹ As such, the *surau* manuscripts stand as written monuments to the dynamic oral teaching practices that animated these institutions. These manuscripts are mostly composed in Arabic, while those written in Malay are heavily laden with Arabic concepts, vocabulary, and technical expressions. Translation emerges as an integral aspect of engagement with the manuscripts, indispensable both for understanding the content and for facilitating the teaching process. Grasping the modes of translation employed within the *surau* tradition thus offers critical insights into the mechanisms of education and knowledge transmission in these institutions.

This article investigates the translation tradition of *surau* communities in the Minangkabau world, with a focus on interlinear translation. However, I argue that the existing *surau* corpus suggests that interlinear translation cannot be studied in isolation from the broader manuscript culture of the *surau*. Accordingly, this study examines interlinear translation in close connection with other translation practices also found within the *surau* tradition. In doing so, it draws on the manuscript collection of *Surau Simaung* in Sijunjung,

Dissertation, The Australian National University, 1993), 35.

7 Drakard, "A Kingdom of Words," 1–15; Christine Dobbin, *Kebangkitan Islam dalam Ekonomi Petani yang Sedang Berubah, Sumatra Tengah, 1784–1847*, trans. Lillian D. Tedjasudana (INIS, 1992), 144; Anwar, "Minangkabau," 80.

8 Azyumardi Azra, *Surau: Pendidikan Islam Tradisi dalam Transisi dan Modernisasi* (PT. Logos Wacana Ilmu, 2003); Oman Fathurahman, "Naskah dan Rekonstruksi Sejarah Lokal Islam; Contoh Kasus dari Minangkabau," *Wacana* 7, no. 2 (2005).

9 Pramono, *Khazanah Naskah Minangkabau* (Penerbit Erka, 2018), 7.

10 Yusuf, *Katalogus Manuskrip*; Pramono, *Khazanah Naskah Minangkabau*.

11 Arif Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable: The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice," *Indonesia and the Malay World*, January 4, 2024, 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2264672>.

West Sumatra, which houses eighty-eight manuscripts encompassing 209 texts across a wide range of Islamic disciplines, including *taṣawwuf*, *kalām*, Qur'an and *tafsīr*, hadith, *fiqh*, history, *falak*, and Arabic linguistics.¹² The majority of these texts are Arabic with Malay translations and annotations, and even original Malay compositions frequently contain Arabic expressions—whether Qur'anic verses, prophetic traditions, or technical terminology—most of which are accompanied by translations. Although many of the texts are undated, those with dates predominantly originate from the late eighteenth to early nineteenth centuries. Earlier materials—or at least copies of texts from the earlier period—are also present, including works attributed to earlier Malay authors, such as 'Abd al-Ra'ūf al-Sinkilī (d. 1693), Shams al-Dīn al-Sumatrānī (d. 1630), and 'Abd al-Ṣamad al-Falimbānī (d. c. 1789). In light of its breadth and diversity, the Surau Simaung collection may be considered representative of the broader surau textual tradition.

To uncover the translation tradition of the surau manuscript culture, this study is guided by two central questions: first, the role and positioning of Arabic and Malay within the translation practices of surau manuscripts; and second, the origins of grammatical literalism, a feature often associated with interlinear translation in the surau tradition. Both questions reveal important aspects of surau manuscript culture, in which the majority of texts take the form of occasional interlinear translations, with Arabic functioning as the primary language of discourse and Malay serving a secondary, supportive role. This suggests that the Surau Simaung collection represents the apex of the surau textual tradition, where engagement with Arabic had become institutionalized. Moreover, the meticulous attention to fine-grained Arabic grammar evident in the collection indicates that, for surau communities, translation was not merely a matter of rendering Arabic into Malay, but a deeper intellectual endeavour aimed at mastering the Islamic sciences through post-classical engagement with Arabic texts.

The Surau Manuscript Tradition: Between Arabic and Malay

Ronit Ricci has identified three distinct paradigms to the translation of Islamic manuscripts in Malay and Javanese literary traditions. The first paradigm, which she terms “holistic translation,” involves rendering and adapting entire works from Arabic or Persian into Malay or Javanese. These translations often preserve overarching storylines, dialogic structures, or theological themes, but also display considerable flexibility, as translators reshape the texts to suit local literary tastes and their own agendas in disseminating Islamic knowledge. The second paradigm transpires at the sentence level, in which Arabic phrases are immediately followed on the page by their Malay or Javanese counterparts. These renderings range from highly literal to paraphrastic or interpretive, where the bilingual layout often invites readers or listeners to move back and forth between languages. The third paradigm is interlinear

¹² The current caretaker himself notes that the digital copies made available through the DREAMSEA Project does not represent the entirety of his holdings. All sources consulted in this study are drawn from the digital copies of the DREAMSEA Project, under the collection code DS 0043. (<https://www.hmmcloud.org/dreamsea/manuscripts.php?country=&tags=&city=&author=&library=Surau+Simaung&language=&projnum=&writingSupport=&title=&script=&searchType=1>)

translation, in which Malay or Javanese words are inserted between the lines of Arabic text in a near word-for-word fashion. This mode lays bare the mechanics of translation, revealing how translators grappled with the linguistic structure of Arabic while attempting to maintain clarity in the target language. Among the three, it is the most linguistically meticulous and closely tied to the grammatical features of the source text.¹³

With a minor adjustment, Ricci's categorization proves particularly useful for examining the tradition of Arabic translation within the Minangkabau surau context, as all three paradigms are represented in the surau manuscript collection. Within the Surau Simaung collection, texts belonging to the first paradigm, holistic translation, are largely derivative of certain more popular works. The most prominent examples are texts concerning the *Sifat dua puluh* (the twenty attributes of God), which are derived from the textual traditions of al-Sanūsī and Tilimsānī.¹⁴ One narrative text, *Hikayat Puti Bilqis* (The Tale of Princess Bilqis) also appears to follow this paradigm, although further investigation is required to determine the original Arabic source from which it was translated.¹⁵ Texts following this first paradigm are, in principle, monolingual. However, given that the whole collection of Surau Simaung largely consists of Islamic works, it is unsurprising that Arabic words and quotations frequently appear within the texts of this translation paradigm.

For the second paradigm, while Ricci refers to this as sentence-level translation, this article adopts the term *running-sequential translation*, as the same format may also apply to smaller units, such as phrases, rather than complete sentences. This adjustment more accurately captures the granularity of translation practices in the surau tradition. This translation paradigm is characterized by a bilingual layout in which the Arabic source text appears first, followed directly by its Malay translation. The Arabic segments may range from a single phrase to sentences of several lines, sometimes extending to half of, or an entire page. The Malay translation continues along the same horizontal line or textual flow, resulting in a unified manuscript in which source and translation are read as part of a continuous sequence. A variation of this format involves texts primarily composed in Malay but interspersed with Arabic expressions—drawn from the Qur'an, hadith, Islamic treatises, or technical terminology—each followed by a corresponding Malay explanation.

These texts are written in *Jawi*, a modified Arabic script adapted to represent Malay phonemes absent in Arabic. To visually distinguish between the two languages, scribes commonly used red ink for Arabic and black for Malay. In some cases, verbal cues such as *artinya* (its meaning is) are also employed to signal transitions. In the absence of colour differentiation or verbal markers, however, the visual uniformity of the script and layout can

13 Ronit Ricci, "Story, Sentence, Single Word: Translation Paradigms in Javanese and Malay Islamic Literature," in *A Companion to Translation Studies*, by Sandra Bermann and Catherine Porter, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 86 (West Sussex: Wiley Blackwell, 2014), 543–56; For interlinear translation, see also: Ronit Ricci, "Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation," *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80, <https://doi.org/10.1163/24056480-00101008>.

14 Philipp Bruckmayr, "The Šarḥ/Ḥāšiya Phenomenon in Southeast Asia: From al-Sanūsī's Umm al-Barāhīn to Malay Sifat Dua Puluh Literature," *MIDÉO. Mélanges de l'Institut Dominicain d'études Orientales*, no. 32 (May 15, 2017): 27–52.

15 DS 0043 00007.

obscure the bilingual structure, making the presence of translation less readily apparent to untrained readers.

Examples 1 and 2 below are excerpts from *Murād al-‘ishq* (the desire of love) of Shams al-Dīn al-Sumatrānī (d. 1039/1630).¹⁶ This text is written entirely in black ink. As such, the visual aspect alone does not indicate that it contains an Arabic text accompanied by a Malay translation. The two samples illustrate how Arabic words are translated sequentially into Malay within a sentence, with the translation often presented in an appositive phrase or clause, resulting in a multilayered sentence structure. I have provided a literal English translation for both examples, along with visual markers to aid understanding. Words in **bold** represent Arabic terms or expressions, those that are underlined are their translations, and *italicized* words are verbal cues that connect the two. The integration between translation and source text makes this format challenging to read, but it reveals how the practice of translation facilitated the encounter with, and introduction of Arabic terminology to a Malay audience.

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1. Maka inilah kitab yang menghimpun pada menyatakan tauhid dan hati ta’līf shaikh Shamsy al-Dīn ma’nānya daripada **kitab tasawwuf** *artinya perkataan pada ilmu **sūfī** artinya orang tahqīq yang suci i’tiqādnya*, karangan Shaikh Muḥy al-Dīn ibn ‘Arabī **qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu** *artinya dipersuci Allah ta’ālā rahasianya*.

This is the book that gathers explanations of tawḥīd and the (spiritual) heart, composed by Shaykh Shams al-Dīn; which means it is **a book of taṣawwuf**—*that is, a work on **sūfī** knowledge—referring to people of realization (tahqīq), whose faith is pure*, authored by Shaykh Muḥy al-Dīn ibn ‘Arabī, **qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu**—*meaning, may Allah Most High sanctify his inner reality*.¹⁷

2. Maka hati ‘ārif yang **nūrānī itu** *artinya hati yang Cahaya itu* amat besar lagi amat luas daripada segala alam, sehingga daripada ‘arash pun amat luas, maka daripada pihak amat besarnya dan amat luas dan amat **latifnya** *artinya halus* maka ia menerima tajalli dhāt Allah ta’ālā ...

So the heart of the ‘ārif that is **luminous (nūrānī)**—*that means the heart that is **Light***—is extremely vast and exceedingly expansive beyond all the worlds, even more expansive than the Throne (‘arsh). So, from the aspect of its immensity, vastness, and **latīf**—*that is, its fineness*—it receives the tajallī (divine manifestation) of the Essence (dhāt) of Allah, the Exalted...

Not all translations that belong to this category are as complex as the two examples above. *Zahrāt al-murīd fī bayān kalimat al-tawḥīd* (the flower of the seeker in elucidating the word of Divine unity), attributed to ‘Abd al-Ṣamad al-Falimbānī,¹⁸ and an untitled treatise by ‘Abd

¹⁶ DS 0043 00018, 41v-42v

¹⁷ I intentionally set aside stylistic conventions concerning bolding or italicization in this and similar sentences in order to more clearly distinguish between the original terms, their translations, and the verbal cues that serve as bridges between the two.

¹⁸ DS 0043 00008

Fig. 2 *Sharḥ umm al-barāhīn* or *Tilimsāni* by ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad ibn ‘Umar ibn Ibrāhīm al-Tilimsānī (d. 897/1492), The DREAMSEA Project, DS 0043 00087, illustrating the typical pattern of occasional interlinear translation found in the surau manuscript tradition

al-Raʿūf al-Singkīlī¹⁹ consisting of seven theological questions and their answers, present translations whose format makes for a more readable text. In these texts, not only are the Arabic and Malay sections distinguished by colour—red for Arabic and black for Malay—but the layout also ensures that the Arabic text completes a sentence or a short section before the Malay translation follows. Rather than interweaving Arabic phrases with their translations, these works place the Arabic and Malay components in distinct positions, each forming a coherent unit on its own, albeit arranged along a sequential, continuous line.

The third translation paradigm observed in Surau Simaung manuscript collections is interlinear translation. Interlinear translation is characterized by its format, in which the translation is written between lines that are spaced out to allow each translated word to appear directly beneath its corresponding word in the source text. This layout enables the translator to pursue a word-for-word rendering and to attend to even the smallest linguistic features of the original, wherever possible. Ricci notes that while interlinear translation does not challenge the notion that a “perfect” translation is ultimately unattainable, it nonetheless comes closer to that ideal than other translation models. This is because interlinear translation seeks “to find equivalents for even small grammatical particles like prepositions or suffixes—an attempt that can go so far in trying to replicate the original text’s syntax that the translated sentence compromises its semantic meaning.”²⁰

A broad overview of the manuscript collection at Surau Simaung reveals two important observations. First, that interlinear translation is typically applied on an occasional basis as the available translation of the original Arabic text does not constitute a complete or meaningful sentence in itself. Second, Malay translation is not the only material appearing beneath the lines; the interlinear material is more diverse than translation.

In general, there are three types of interlinear material in the manuscript tradition of Surau Simaung. The first two are verbal: Malay translations and Arabic glosses. The Malay translations provide equivalents of the Arabic source text and are predominantly rendered in either a literal or paraphrastic style. Arabic glosses, on the other hand, consist of brief explanatory notes attached to specific Arabic words or phrases. These glosses can be broadly categorized into three types:

(1) cultural glosses, such as the insertion of *ism al-balad* (the name of the country) when a city is mentioned;

(2) grammatical glosses, including clarifications of an implicit subject following a verb—e.g., identifying *Allāh*, *Muḥammad*, or another figure after *qāla* (he said)—or the use of words to indicate grammatical positions such as *mafʿūl bih* (object), and *ḥāl* (adverbial accusative) beneath the relevant words; and

(3) technical glosses, which offer citations from other sources or define key concepts. In didactic-linguistic texts covering subjects such as *nahw*, *ṣarf*, and *maʿānī*, a common form of technical gloss is the insertion of sample sentences to illustrate specific linguistic unit or

19 DS 0043 00019, 290v. – 299r.

20 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 69.

function. In texts on *ṣarf*, basic verb-inflection patterns are often provided.²¹ Texts on *tajwīd*, which concerns the proper recitation of the Qur'an, may include examinations of recitation rules, as exemplified in treatments of sura al-Fātiḥa.²²

The third type of interlinear material commonly found in the manuscript tradition of Surau Simaung is non-verbal, consisting of visual marks that serve as reading aids. These marks often reflect personal patterns of use, as the style and function of such annotations may vary from one manuscript to another. Nevertheless, several recurring practices can be identified. One frequently observed function is itemization: when a text lists multiple elements within a category, each item is marked in an identical way—sometimes simply with a red upper line—to indicate that they belong to the same conceptual group. Another common function is grammatical clarification, where marks are used to connect pronouns with their referents or verbs with their corresponding subjects. Less frequently, these non-verbal marks serve a punctuation-like role, signalling specific points within the texts or marking the closure of a discourse unit. Furthermore, in manuscripts that include marginal notes, the connecting marks linking words in the main text to their explanations in the margins are often inscribed beneath the lines as well.

There is a fundamental distinction between the first two translation paradigms—holistic and running-sequential translation—and interlinear translation within the Surau Simaung manuscript collection. In the former, Malay functions as the primary language of discourse, while in the latter, Arabic occupies that dominant position, with Malay serving a supporting role.

To clarify this point, let us revisit the examples previously cited for holistic and running-sequential translation. Three texts were discussed in relation to the running-sequential paradigm: *Murād al-‘ishq*, *Zahrāt al-murīd*, and an untitled treatise by ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf. *Murād al-‘ishq* is essentially a Malay prose composition enriched with Arabic vocabulary and conceptual elements, in which Arabic terms are immediately followed by their Malay translations. In this respect, the text shares a defining feature with works in the holistic translation category, *Hikayat Puti Bilqis* and *Sifat dua puluh*, in that they are essentially Malay texts.

Zahrāt al-murīd and the untitled work of ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf present a different case. Both authors state in their respective introductions that the original compositions were written in Arabic, and that the translations were produced in response to specific requests. This suggests the existence of an earlier monolingual Arabic version—now likely lost—and a later bilingual version, complemented with Malay translation, which survives as part of the Surau Simaung collection. Because many Arabic theological and philosophical terms in the original could not be adequately conveyed through literal translation alone, extended elaboration became necessary in the translated version. This format corresponds to what Mahmood Kooria terms *intermittent translation*, a sub-category of commentarial translation, in which the Arabic text is accompanied by extensive explanations provided by the author or translator. In this context, brief Arabic statements are frequently followed by lengthy Malay commentaries—at times extending over several pages. Arabic functions here as a marker of scholarly authority, while the Malay translation and explanation serves the pedagogical needs of a local audience. Considering this

21 DS 0043 00045, 20r

22 DS 0043 00008, 70r

production history, it can be argued that it is the Malay explanatory content, rather than the Arabic original, that constitutes the *raison d'être* of both texts.

Interlinear translation, by contrast, reflects a more sustained and institutionalized practice of close reading and engagement with Arabic texts. While the previously discussed texts suggest that direct interaction with Arabic was primarily undertaken by translators—typically established scholars—who produced Malay translations for general readers, interlinear texts indicate a broader context of engagement of Arabic. In these works, rather than simply providing ready-made Malay translations, scholars taught the Arabic texts directly to students, employing the various interlinear materials described above. This approach embedded the practice of engaging with Arabic more deeply within educational settings.

In other words, these texts, within the surau educational setting, were intended to be read and understood in their Arabic form, with the Malay translation occupying a secondary, supportive role. The diverse interlinear materials described above reinforce this point. The second type of Arabic gloss—namely, grammatical glosses—suggests that the texts were first approached with a conscious awareness of Arabic linguistic structures. In the interlinear Malay translations, this linguistic orientation often shaped the Malay renderings, which frequently make more sense when interpreted through the lens of Arabic grammar (a point to which we will return in the following sub-section). Moreover, the technical glosses—consisting of partial citations drawn from other sources—also tend to refer to Arabic-language references. As a result, the proportion of Malay content in many of these texts is significantly lower than that of the Arabic. This indicates that Arabic defines the identity of these texts, with the Malay translation serving as one of several comprehension aids, alongside Arabic glosses and non-verbal interlinear elements such as the marks mentioned earlier.

Texts with full line-by-line interlinear Malay translation are, of course, also available. In a text of this kind the Malay translation plays a more prominent role compared to other kinds of interlinear intervention. This kind of translation is most likely intended for beginners, as evidenced by the introductory level of the texts' content. In the Surau Simaung collection, the texts that fall into this category are *Ādāb al-muta'allim* (the etiquette of the student),²³ *Bayān al-sirr al-ghayb wa al-shahāda min al-kashf wa al-sirar al-rububiyya* (elucidation of the secret of the unseen and the visible realms through unveiling and the mysteries of Divine lordship),²⁴ an untitled treatise on *tajwīd* (DS 0043 00008, p. 80v), and two texts on Arabic morphology (DS 0043 00045; DS 0043 00034). In these texts, the words of the translation are organized into a coherent sentence that can be comprehended on its own. Even without the original text, the translated version, although it may not sound entirely natural and idiomatic to modern readers, is still understandable. In these texts the Malay translation plays a particularly important role, and given that they are elementary in nature, it is acceptable that other forms of interlinear materials are largely sidelined.

23 DS 0043 00014

24 DS 0043 00005 p. 101v

Behind Grammatical Literalism

In his pioneering 1899 article, the Dutch scholar Ph. S. van Ronkel demonstrated the apparent influence of Arabic syntactic structure on Malay language through works of translation.²⁵ Peter G. Riddell similarly observed this tendency in a Malay rendering of a Qur'an commentary—a phenomenon he terms *translationese*.²⁶ In another study, Ricci further illustrates how interlinear translation reflects shifts in word order, subject–verb position, tense, and emphasis, resulting from the practice of word-for-word translation. In a particularly striking formulation, she characterizes this phenomenon as one in which Arabic grammar “glues together” Malay vocabulary in the interlinear rendering. She concludes her observations with an open question: how and why did such models come into being?²⁷

The phenomenon of Malay vocabulary being structured according to Arabic grammatical rules is referred to in this article as *grammatical literalism*. While literal translation is conventionally understood as a word-for-word rendering from one language to another, the grammatical disparities between Arabic and Malay—such as those involving tense, number, and gender—mean that many features explicit in Arabic remain unexpressed in Malay. This discrepancy prompts translators to accommodate these differences, often at the expense of the natural grammatical structure of Malay as the target language. This section explores such issues of grammatical literalism in the surau manuscript tradition, demonstrating that its translation practices are consistent with the observations made by the aforementioned scholars. It will also consider a possible answer to the question Ricci has raised regarding the origins of such translation models.

The preceding section has demonstrated that translation constitutes only one among several forms of interlinear intervention within the surau manuscript tradition. It has also been shown that the majority of surau manuscript collections containing translation feature interlinear translation applied on an occasional basis. In view of this, to what extent can such interlinear intervention be meaningfully associated with literalism, given that the translation appears only in truncated or fragmentary form?

We are fortunate that, although limited in number, the surau manuscript tradition preserves texts containing line-by-line interlinear translation, as previously noted. These texts enable a more sustained engagement with the question of grammatical literalism in translation practices within the surau manuscript tradition, and thus serve as important points of reference in discussions of other, more occasional interlinear texts. The following example offers a compelling illustration of the tendency towards literalism in interlinear translation:

25 Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat Arab Terhadap Tatakalimat Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528.

26 Peter G. Riddell, “Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay,” *Studia Islamika* 9, no. 2 (2002): 23, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/sdi.v9i1.672>.

27 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 76.

3. *I'lam anna al-fi'l 'alā ayy binā' kāna lā yakhlū min an yakūna ṣaḥīḥan aw muḍā'afan ... (Know that the verb, in whatever pattern it may be, is not devoid of being either ṣaḥīḥ or muḍā'af ...)*²⁸

Ketahui olehmu bahwasanya segala fi'l atas barang bina ada iya tiada sunyi daripada bahwa keadaannya bina ṣaḥīḥ atau bina muḍā'af ... (Know by you that every fi'l upon whatever bina it may be, its state is not devoid of being (either) bina ṣaḥīḥ or bina muḍā'af...)

The original Arabic sentence in this example is relatively straightforward; nonetheless, the translator appears to have attempted to render each word individually, maintaining a strict one-to-one correspondence between source text and translation. The phrase *olehmu* (by you) is used to translate an unexpressed pronoun functioning as the object of the imperative verb *i'lam* (know). The semantic subtlety conveyed by the definite article *al-* in *al-fi'l*, which implies *shumūl* (wholeness), is also translated, resulting in *al-fi'l* being rendered as *segala fi'l* (every *fi'l*). The term *fi'l* itself is left untranslated, as it functions here as a technical linguistic concept. The appositive phrase *'alā ayy binā' kāna* (in whatever pattern it may be) is rendered word for word, producing an unnatural formulation: *atas barang bina ada iya* (upon whatever bina it may be). A similarly literal rendering of *min an yakūna* (being either) likewise results in an awkward construction. The unnatural nature of the translation of *kāna* and *yakūna* (both mean “[to] be” in the different declensions) in this example is entirely consistent with Van Ronkel’s observation of the same issue.²⁹ In such cases, Riddell’s observation seems particularly apt: even Malay readers “probably had even greater headaches trying to understand” *atas barang bina dia*.³⁰ It is only by referring back to the Arabic sentence that one can make proper sense of the intended meaning.

It has been noted that the primary distinction between line-by-line interlinear translation and occasional translation lies in the fact that the former yields a complete sentence in translation, while the latter provides only individual words or particles without forming a coherent or meaningful expression. Based on the way grammatical literalism is explained above, one way to identify literalism in occasional interlinear translation is to assume that close attention to linguistic details—such as gender, number, and tense—may serve as an indicator of a grammatically literal rendering. This assumption rests on the understanding that occasional translation essentially constitutes a written record of oral translation practices that took place in didactic settings. If such details as gender and number inflection, or other subtle features, are inscribed in occasional interlinear form, this suggests that they were also observed during the oral translation process. It was not uncommon for oral translation to be accompanied by extended explanatory remarks. However, the full extent of the oral translator’s elaboration was not necessarily transcribed onto the written page, thereby resulting in the fragmentary form of occasional interlinear translation preserved in the manuscript.

²⁸ DS 0043 00045, 8r.

²⁹ Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatalimat*, 17.

³⁰ Riddell, “Literal Translation,” 23.

From this perspective, it becomes evident that manuscripts containing occasional interlinear translation demonstrate a clear tendency towards literal translation. This is due to the fact that such manuscripts reflect the translator's or reader's attentiveness to fine-grained linguistic details, even when the translation is not exhaustive. The manifestations of this attentiveness are varied. Figs 3, 4, and 5 illustrate how occasional interlinear translation reveals the translator's deep grammatical sensibilities. In Fig. 3, for instance, the word *al-jumal* (sentences) is translated with *segala* (all). Here, *segala* does not represent a full lexical translation of *al-jumal* but rather reflects a partial rendering—specifically, the semantic import of the definite article *al-* which semantically signifies *shumūl* (wholeness). The noun *jumal* itself is left untranslated.

In Fig. 4, the word *shahāda* (a testimony) is translated as *sempurna* (perfect). As with the previous example, this translation does not reflect the entire lexical content of the Arabic word but instead captures its semantic connotation, its being grammatically a *maf'ūl muṭlaq* (cognate accusative). That is, the translator chooses to convey the emphatic or intensifying function of the word rather than translate the noun *shahāda* directly. Also in Fig. 5, only a single word is translated across two visible lines—namely, *al-salāfīn* (kings), which is rendered as *raja2* (the numeral indicating reduplication, hence “raja-raja” or “kings,” to denote plurality). This translation highlights the plural form of the Arabic original. This choice underscores the translator's attention to number inflection—an important grammatical detail that might otherwise be lost in an occasional interlinear context.

These examples collectively demonstrate that occasional translation, while fragmentary on the surface, is in fact highly attentive to the structural and semantic details of the Arabic text. It reflects a deep engagement with the linguistic substance of the source, despite not offering a full linear rendering. Though it may appear random or haphazard, a closer examination of texts featuring such translation reveals that most basic verb inflections and grammatical features are, in fact, accommodated within the translation. This way, the occasional written interventions between the lines function not merely as translations but as interpretive cues or prompts that facilitate oral reading, teaching, and comprehension of the source text as well as reinforcement of Arabic grammatical knowledge.

Fig. 3 *Qaṭr al-nadā'* by Abū 'Abdullāh Jamāl al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf ibn Hishām al-Anṣārī (d. 761/1360), DS 0043 00006, 1v

Fig. 4 *al-Sanūsī* by Abū ‘Abdillāh Abū Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf al-Sanūsī al-Ḥusaynī (d. 895/1490), DS 0043 00019, 178r

Fig. 5 *Tanbīh al-māshi* by ‘Abd al-Ra‘uf al-Sinkīlī al-Jāwī (d. 1693), DS 0043 00018, 12v

However, the Surau Simaung collections show that such literalism is not the exclusive property of interlinear translation. Running-sequential translation also follows the same tendency. Note that the source consulted by Riddell in his aforementioned study for the argument of *translationese* is not an interlinear translation. Just like the case with Ricci’s source in the Sri Lankan Malay manuscript, example 4 follows the original Arabic that commences the clause with a verb-subject order, something that is not conventional for Malay.³¹

4. *qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu* artinya dipersucikan Allah ta‘ālā rahasianya ([may] sanctified Allah his secret) which means sanctified [by] Allah may He be Exalted his secret)³²

³¹ Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 72.

³² In this and the following example, the underlined English corresponds to the underlined Arabic sentence.

5. ... wa ja'ala al-jannata maskanahu wa mathwāhu dan yang menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan akan dia kediamannya (...and He made Paradise his dwelling and his abode and that which makes Paradise a dwelling of a believer and it his abode)

Example 5 provides a more compelling illustration of how Arabic syntax, even outside an interlinear format, structurally binds Malay vocabulary to the original. This includes elements that are not explicitly present in the Arabic text but are syntactically implied. Each word in the Malay translation is anchored to an Arabic counterpart: *wa* (and) becomes *dan* (and), *ja'ala* (he made) becomes *menjadikan* (makes), *al-jannata* (the garden) becomes *surga* (paradise), and *maskanahu* (his dwelling) is rendered as *tempat mukmin* (a dwelling of a believer). In this last case, the pronoun *-hu* in *maskanahu* is resolved by referring back to *mu'min*, a noun mentioned earlier in the text. Notably, the word *yang* (that/which) in *dan yang menjadikan* (that which makes) has no direct lexical counterpart in the Arabic, but its presence is informed by the syntactic role of *wa* (and) at the beginning of the expression. This conjunction links *ja'ala* (he made) to a preceding verb, *hafiẓa* (he protected), which itself follows *alladhī* (those), a relative pronoun typically translated as *yang* in Malay. Thus, the translator's insertion of *yang* signals an awareness of the underlying conjunctive structure of the Arabic.

The phrase *dan akan dia kediamannya* (and it his abode) for *wa mathwāhu* (and his abode) reflects an impressive syntactic sensitivity. Here, *dan* (and) corresponds to *wa* (and), functioning as a conjunction linking *maskanahu* (his dwelling) and *mathwāhu* (his abode). A straightforward translation might have rendered the passage as *menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan kediamannya* ([to] make Paradise a dwelling of a believer and his abode). However, the translator chooses *menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan akan dia kediamannya* (makes Paradise a dwelling of a believer and [make] it his abode), revealing a distinct grammatical interpretation. Rather than viewing *wa* as connecting *maskanahu* and *mathwāhu* directly, the translator appears to interpret *wa* as linking two complete predicates: *al-jannata maskanahu* and (*hiya*) *mathwāhu*. The subject *hiya* is not textually present but is understood through *ellipsis* (*muqaddara*), a common feature in Arabic whereby syntactic elements are omitted yet implied. It refers back to *al-jannata* (the garden), a feminine noun. Accordingly, the phrase *akan dia kediamannya* reflects this: *akan* indicates the object, *dia* realizes the elided pronoun *hiya*, and *kediamannya* renders *mathwāhu*, with the possessive *-nya* (his) pointing back to *mu'min*.

In his study, Riddell argues that the tendency towards *translationese* is inherited from the literal scriptural translation that was observed by 'Abd al-Ra'ūf al-Sinkīlī, the author of *Tarjumān al-mustafīd* that he consulted, while the *Tarjumān* author was in the Middle East.³³ This argument situates the Qur'anic text and its translation at the core of a literal impulse. Van Ronkel in his study also emphasized the role of the Qur'an in this respect alongside *fiqh*.³⁴ The manuscripts from Surau Simaung, however, suggest that this technique of translation may not directly related to scriptural translation, nor is it exclusive to *fiqh*

33 Riddell, "Literal Translation," 10.

34 Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalamat*, 37.

literature. Rather, it derives from the prevailing approach to studying Islamic texts within the tradition of post-classical scholasticism.

Commentary and gloss constituted the dominant modes of intellectual composition in post-classical Islam, spanning the sixteenth to nineteenth centuries.³⁵ Significantly, the majority of texts in the surau collection fall within this category. Texts featuring running-sequential translation, although original compositions by Malay authors, are deeply rooted in Arabic Islamic scholastic works. They function primarily as commentaries on selected passages extracted from these Arabic source texts as well as their own texts.³⁶ Likewise, texts with interlinear translation are rarely devoid of glosses and marginal annotations. Another key feature of the post-classical intellectual tradition was its sustained preoccupation with the lexical, rhetorical, and logical dimensions of the commented-upon texts. Within this approach, substantial portions of the commentary are often devoted to lexicographical treatment of individual words.³⁷ The surau texts strongly resonate with this mode of inquiry, and this orientation is clearly reflected in their translation practices.

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Arabic language texts occupy a prominent place in the Surau Simaung collection. The most illustrative examples in this context are works belonging to the genres of *tarkīb* (structure; composition) and *i'rāb* (the system of declension). These are derivative, commentarial genres that focus on the linguistic analysis of a base text. It remains a subject of inquiry whether *tarkīb* and *i'rāb* represent distinct genres or are essentially the same with different names. The evidence from Surau Simaung, however, indicates that *i'rāb* tends to involve a more detailed analysis than *tarkīb*. In the collection, we find three different copies of *Tarkīb al-ʿawāmil*, one copy of *Tarkīb al-Ājurrūmiyya*, and one of *I'rāb matan al-kāfiya*.

The *tarkīb/i'rāb* genre demonstrates that such linguistic analysis was not merely applied as a method of examining texts, but also gave rise to a distinct genre of intellectual endeavour in its own right. Each of these texts investigates the linguistic features of individual words within their respective base texts—namely, *al-ʿAwāmil*, *Ājurrūmiyya*, and *Matan al-kāfiya*. They explore the types of words or particles mentioned, their syntactic positions, grammatical inflection (*i'rāb*), and morphological patterns, number, semantic connotation, and other relevant linguistic features. Fig. 6 illustrates how *tarkīb* functions. The text in red represents the base text, while the black text—breaking down the base text, largely into individual words—constitutes a linguistic analysis of each word or phrase from the Arabic source. This particular page offers only minimal commentary for most of the words, although it is not uncommon to find pages containing more elaborate explanations. This analysis extends beyond the level of individual words, encompassing phrases and clauses as well.

35 Ahmed El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition* (Princeton University Press, 2020), 9; 31.

36 Mahmood Kooria, *Islamic Law in Circulation: Shāfiʿī Texts across the Indian Ocean and the Mediterranean*, Cambridge Studies in Islamic Civilization (Cambridge University Press, 2022), 327.

37 El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics*, 35.

Fig. 6 *Tarkīb al-‘awāmil*, DS 0043 00004

The concept of ellipsis (*muqaddara*) is integral to understanding the practice of Malay translation. In Arabic grammar, the principle is that a sentence must complete all the basic structural elements, whether it is a nominal or verbal sentence. When a structural element is missing, it is the reader’s duty to analyse the construction and supply the implied component.

Fig. 6 illustrates how the *basmala* formula is linguistically analysed in the *tarkīb* genre. The full *basmala* phrase—*bi-smi-‘l-lāh al-rahmān al-rahīm*—is divided into four segments, each written in red ink. Interspersed between these segments is the grammatical explanation, written in black ink. The first segment, *bi-smi* (in the name [of]), is analysed beginning with the identification of *bā’* as a *ḥarf jarr* (preposition) and *ism* as a *majrūr* (a noun governed by a preposition), resulting from the effect of *bā’*. The analysis then proceeds to determine the grammatical position of *bi-smi* as a phrase linked to an ellipsis (*al-maḥzūf*). The text then provides the resolution, stating *taqdīruhu abtadī‘u bi-smi...* (its *taqdīr*, “implied phrase,” is: I commence in the name [of]...). This analysis explains the way authors and translators render the *basmala* whenever composing or copying a text, by expressions such as *Kumulai membaca kitab ini...* (I begin to read this book...) or *Kumulai risalah ini...* (I begin this treatise...). This case illustrates an expansion of meaning proposed by translators, transmitting an Arabic linguistic examination of the sentence into Malay.

The manuscript collection of Surau Simaung demonstrates that this mode of intellectual inquiry remained deeply embedded within surau communities. The study of Arabic undertaken in these settings was not merely a theoretical endeavour grounded in standard textbooks—such as the *Ājurrūmiyya*, *Qaṭr al-nadā’*, *Alfiyya* Ibn Mālik, *al-Kāfiya*, and *al-‘Awāmil*, together with their accompanying *sharḥ* (commentaries)—but was also complemented by practical engagement with the *tarkīb* and *ī‘rāb* traditions. This analytical approach was not limited to linguistic texts; works from other disciplines were likewise

subjected to grammatical scrutiny. Although we currently lack evidence of texts in other fields—such as *kalām*, mysticism, and others³⁸—developing into distinct genres akin to *tarkīb* and *iʿrāb*, linguistic annotations, whether brief or elaborate, are nonetheless commonly found beneath the lines or in the margins of many texts. Not limited to interlinear translation, this grammatical attentiveness is also reflected in running-sequential translations. For instance, when ʿAbd al-Ṣamad explicates the core theological formula *lā ilāha illā-ʿl-lāh* (there is no God but Allah), he begins by analysing the type of *lā* used in the phrase and outlining its semantic implications.

Translation in this context reflects a deeper concern on the part of Malay translators from the surau community than merely bridging two different languages. Snouck Hurgronje’s observation of the difficulties faced by Southeast Asian Muslim communities in learning and reading Arabic can be understood as their effort to overcome the language barrier—particularly given Arabic’s considerably more complex grammatical structure compared to Malay.³⁹ While the difference in language is undeniably a significant factor in any act of translation, the tradition of Arabic translation in the surau goes beyond this. Linguistic difference is part of the puzzle, but not its foundation. What lies at the core is textual examination.

For this reason, the conventional definition of translation—such as: “reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source-language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style”⁴⁰—fails to capture the nature of translation within the Malay/Minangkabau surau tradition. This textual corpus of Surau Simaung shows that for the surau communities, translation was not primarily a matter of seeking equivalents in Malay, but first and foremost an exercise in textual examination. The accuracy of translation lay not in finding a natural equivalent in Malay, but in the successful exploration of all the grammatical details of the Arabic text. Clarity lies not in seamless, idiomatic Malay expression, but rather in the strongest resonance with the original semantic connotation of the Arabic expression. Ricci suggests that interlinear translation “divulges the detailed mechanism of translating prepositions, markers of gender, case, and tense into a very different linguistic context.”⁴¹ Indeed, the actual practice of translation was the transfer of Arabic textual analysis into Malay. For the surau communities, translation was an act of textual analysis of Arabic in the vernacular; it thus became the vernacular practice of a post-classical linguistic examination of texts.

38 A comparable genre of text is found in *tajwīd*, in which the author examines the *tajwīd* rules for every individual word of the Qur’an (DS 0043 0008, p. 70r).

39 C. Snouck Hurgronje, *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslems of the East-Indian Archipelago* (Brill, 2007), 284. On this question see Ricci’s article in the present issue.

40 Eugene A. Nida and Charles R. Taber, *The Theory and Practice of Translation* (Brill, 1982), 12.

41 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 78.

Conclusion

The surau functioned as a vibrant ecosystem for the transmission of Islamic texts in the Minangkabau world, where scholars and students engaged in the continuous practice of teaching, reading, and translating texts. The Surau Simaung collection stands as a remarkable testament to this tradition, comprising 88 manuscripts and 209 texts. The collection spans works from the early Malay scholars at the turn of the seventeenth century to texts produced well into the twentieth century, offering a broad and rich corpus for understanding the surau textual tradition.

This study has shown that translation practices in the surau were diverse, encompassing holistic, running-sequential, and interlinear paradigms. Among these, occasional interlinear translation predominates, revealing a distinctive form of grammatical literalism rooted in the Arabic linguistic structure. This grammatical literalism, noted as early as Van Ronkel's observations, reflects a deliberate and nuanced engagement with Arabic grammar, lexicon, and syntax—a reflection of post-classical scholarly practices.

What emerges from the Surau Simaung corpus is not simply a record of Malay translations of Arabic texts, but a vernacularized mode of textual analysis. Translation functioned as an instrument of grammatical inquiry, enabling students to penetrate the structure and meaning of Arabic discourse through the medium of Malay. This approach departs from conventional models of translation as equivalence, and instead foregrounds translation as a pedagogical and analytical act.

At its core, translation in the surau tradition was a vernacular expression of the post-classical Islamic intellectual project. Translation, in this context, was not primarily about finding lexical equivalents in Malay, but fundamentally an exercise in textual analysis. Its accuracy was measured not by how naturally it read in Malay, but by how thoroughly it engaged with the grammatical structure of the Arabic source. Clarity was achieved not through idiomatic fluency, but through the closest possible alignment with the semantic nuance of the original Arabic expression. The surau thus emerges not only as a site of transmission, but as a site of transformation: where Arabic knowledge traditions were not merely received but reconstituted through local, oral, and linguistically exacting modes of engagement.

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